

Rain Resilience of MIMO Ground Stations for LEO Constellations

Oscar Martinez^{1*,2}, Thomas Delamotte², Hervé Legay¹, Andreas Knopp²

¹ *Thales Alenia Space, Toulouse, France.*

² *Chair of Signal Processing, University of the Bundeswehr Munich, Neubiberg, Germany.*

* Corresponding Author: papers@unibw.de

Abstract—Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) is a promising solution to overcome the current feeder bottleneck in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellite constellations. Beyond its higher spectral efficiency, the distributed architecture of MIMO ground stations adds rain robustness to the link, thus improving its availability. This work analyzes the advantages of MIMO for short-range diversity, focusing on the joint probability of rain attenuation. A numerical comparison is performed using MIMO with different antennas counts and a conventional Single-Input Single-Output (SISO) setup with backup antenna. Results demonstrate that MIMO improves the link robustness against rain impairments.

Keywords—MIMO, feeder links, 6G NTN, rain attenuation, short-range diversity.

I. INTRODUCTION

LEO constellations for broadband services have achieved economic success in recent years and are expected to continue growing with the arrival of 6G networks. Anticipating this demand, satellite manufacturers have developed a new generation of payloads, capable of supporting up to four times the first generation throughput and reaching 96 Gbps per satellite [1]. However, ground stations (GSs) have not seen the same capacity improvements, creating a critical service bottleneck. MIMO architectures are emerging as a key enabler to address this challenge. MIMO systems employ multiple coordinated antennas both on-board and on ground, to spatially multiplex data streams [2], [3], [4].

MIMO GSs serving LEO satellites require short antenna separations, typically less than 10 km [2], [5]. The close spacing between antennas allows infrastructure sharing. For example, [2] proposes a 2×2 MIMO where the capacity is maximized when the ground antennas are 3.4 km apart, for a satellite at 600 km of altitude. While most studies have focused on increased spectral efficiency, using multiple antennas on the ground inherently achieve rain de-correlation.

The study in [6] experimentally demonstrated a link budget gain of over 5 dB, by switching between two antennas separated by 1.2 kilometers and operating at 27 GHz. In this paper, we analyze the short-range diversity benefits of LEO MIMO feeder links in the presence of rain attenuation. Section II details the MIMO system configuration and the rain attenuation model for an $N \times M$ scenario. Section III compares the joint rain attenuation probability of different

ground station setups, locations and elevations. Conclusions are presented in Section IV.

II. MIMO AND RAIN ATTENUATION MODEL

A. MIMO Feeder Link for LEO

Figure 1 describes the configuration, where M ground antennas communicate with N antennas on the satellite.

Fig. 1. MIMO ground station architecture for LEO satellites

Ground antennas are closely separated, with separations of no more than $d_g < 10$ km for feeder links in the Ka band. Rain attenuation is dependent on the slant path between the ground site and the satellite. This distance depends on the satellite's elevation angle ϵ , measured from the center of the ground array to the center of the satellite.

B. Generalized Joint Rain Attenuation Probability

The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) provides Recommendation ITU-R P.618-13 [7], which models the joint attenuation probability due to precipitation for two ground antennas. This model was later generalized to M ground antennas in [4] and [3] for the geostationary case.

The model outputs the probability that the rain attenuation at the m -th ground antenna exceeds a threshold a_m , given a satellite elevation ϵ . Mathematically, computed as:

$$P_{\text{overall}}^{\text{MIMO}} = P(A_1 > a_1, \dots, A_M > a_M | \epsilon) = P_r P_a, \quad (1)$$

where P_r is the joint probability that it is raining at all sites and P_a the joint probability of rain attenuation.

1) *Joint probability of rain intensity:*

$$P_r = \int_{R_1}^{\infty} \dots \int_{R_{M_t}}^{\infty} \frac{\exp(-0.5\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{C}_r^{-1} \mathbf{x})}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^M \cdot \det(\mathbf{C}_r)}} d\mathbf{x}. \quad (2)$$

Here, \mathbf{C}_r is the rain correlation, of elements $c_r|_{i,j} = 0.7e^{-d_{i,j}/60} + 0.3e^{-(d_{i,j}/700)^2}$, with $d_{i,j}$ denoting the distance between ground antennas i and j . The thresholds R_m are given by the rain probability at the m -th antenna location $R_m = Q^{-1}(P_m^{Rain}/100)$, where $Q^{-1}(\cdot)$ denotes the inverse complementary cumulative normal distribution, and P_m^{Rain} is the rain probability (in %) at the location m .

2) *Joint probability of rain attenuation:*

$$P_a(\epsilon) = \int_{\bar{a}_1(\epsilon)}^{\infty} \dots \int_{\bar{a}_M(\epsilon)}^{\infty} \frac{\exp(-0.5\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{C}_a^{-1} \mathbf{x})}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^M \cdot \det(\mathbf{C}_a)}} d\mathbf{x}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{C}_a is $c_a|_{i,j} = 0.94e^{-d_{i,j}/30} + 0.06e^{-(d_{i,j}/500)^2}$ and the thresholds are $\bar{a}_m(\epsilon) = \frac{\ln a_m(\epsilon) - m_{\ln A_m(\epsilon)}}{\sigma_{\ln A_m(\epsilon)}}$.

Contrary to the P_r , the statistics of local rain attenuation A_m depend on the slant path length through the rain-affected region. As this distance decreases, or equivalently as the elevation increases, the joint attenuation probability P_a decreases.

3) *SISO case:* For a single antenna, the probability of experiencing a specific attenuation level is given by the rain attenuation probability distribution:

$$P_{\text{overall}}^{\text{SISO}} = \frac{P^{\text{Rain}}}{100} Q\left(\frac{\ln(a) - m_{\ln A}}{\sigma_{\ln A}}\right) \quad (4)$$

III. MIMO SHORT RANGE DIVERSITY COMPARISON

The comparison is conducted across four ground station scenarios. Two reference cases are considered: a single antenna SISO setup and a SISO system with a backup antenna separated by $d_g = 100$ km. Two MIMO configurations are analyzed with $M = 2$ and $M = 4$, each with inter-antenna separation of $d_g = 3.5$ km. The station operates at 30 GHz, where rain attenuation is the dominant atmospheric impairment. Finally, the 600 km altitude orbit is considered.

Fig. 2. Joint rain probability P_{overall} , for different elevation angles. Dashed lines $\epsilon = 30^\circ$ and solid lines $\epsilon = 90^\circ$.

Figure 2 compares P_{overall} at the coverage center $\epsilon = 90^\circ$ and edge $\epsilon = 30^\circ$, assuming identical thresholds across all antennas, i.e., $a_1 = a_m = a$. Satellite elevation significantly affects rain attenuation, with several dB variation across all scenarios. Additionally, MIMO demonstrates lower rain attenuation probability than the single antenna case, even with antenna separations of only 3.5 km.

The advantage of MIMO becomes clear when evaluating the link availability. Assuming a site outage occurs when all antennas exceed the attenuation threshold, MIMO provides a balance between the vulnerable single-antenna systems and long range diversity, avoiding extra infrastructure deployment. Table I summarizes the required link budget margins required to ensure 99.9% link availability ($P_{\text{overall}} < 0.1\%$).

TABLE I
REQUIRED MARGIN [dB] FOR 99.9% AVAILABILITY AT $\epsilon = 30^\circ$

GS location	SISO	$M = 2$	$M = 4$	SISO + Backup
Munich	10.1	6.2	4.1	1.9
New York	16.4	12.1	7.8	3.8
Tokyo	22	15	9.9	5

IV. CONCLUSION

MIMO ground stations are key enablers for future LEO-based services and here are shown to provide short-range diversity benefits. MIMO feeder links can achieve the same link availability as conventional single-antenna architecture with lower rain attenuation margins. Finally, MIMO can ensure priority data is sent via the best antenna.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is part of the HARMONY project which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101072798.

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